

ISSN : 0973-7057

Selected viral and bacterial diseases in reptiles: A report

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Received : 04th September, 2025 ; Revised : 12th October, 2025DOI:-<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21159084>

Abstract- Numerous infectious disorders brought on by bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa can affect reptiles. Turtles, snakes, and other reptiles are susceptible to viral diseases such herpesvirus, fibropapillomatosis, and paramyxovirus, which frequently result in skin lesions, respiratory symptoms, or neurological symptoms. While fungal infections commonly damage skin, lungs, and shells, especially in turtles, bacterial infections, such as *Salmonella* and *Mycoplasma agassizii*, are widespread in both wild and captive populations. The health of reptiles is further threatened by protozoan illnesses including cryptosporidiosis and *Entamoeba* species, which can occasionally cause severe mortality. Considering the significant role reptiles play in the ecosystem, it is critical to understand the risks and issues they face. By dispersing infections, infected reptiles can upset ecosystems, resulting in decreased biodiversity and population losses.

Keywords: Viral Infections, Salmonella, Herpesvirus, Ecosystem, Pathogen

INTRODUCTION

Reptiles are among the most diverse and successful group of vertebrates, including more than 1200 genera and around 11,000 species¹, and are a major component of the global biodiversity, remarkable from an ecological and evolutionary point of view. This class is divided in four orders: Squamata (i.e., 10, 417 species of lizards, snakes, and amphisbaenians), Testudines (i.e., 351 species of turtles and tortoises), Crocodylia (i.e., 24 species of crocodiles, alligators, caimans and gavials), and Rhynchocephalia, the latter represented by a single species of living fossils named tuataras.² Since their emergence during the late Carboniferous period approximately 310–320 million years ago, reptiles have undergone relatively little change in¹ their morphology, biological characteristics, and ecological roles.^{3,4} Concurrently, vectors and pathogens² have evolved alongside reptiles over millions

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of years, potentially shaping the host–vector–pathogen relationships observed today.

Reptiles contribute to ecosystem functioning in multiple ways. They facilitate the movement of genes by participating in seed dispersal, pollination, and epibiosis, and help transfer nutrients from aquatic (freshwater and marine) systems to terrestrial habitats. Additionally, they serve as trophic regulators by controlling prey populations or vegetation, while also providing a food source for higher-level predators. As ecosystem engineers, reptiles promote biodiversity by creating shelters and reproductive sites that benefit other species.⁵

Reptile populations are declining globally as a result of numerous human-driven threats, including habitat destruction, invasive species, environmental pollution, disease, unsustainable land-use practices, and climate change, all of which negatively affect reptile survival.⁶

Reptiles are often overlooked and viewed unfavourably by the general public, a perception that poses

significant obstacles to effective conservation initiatives aimed at protecting their populations.⁷⁻⁹ Currently, over 12,000 species of reptiles are recognised worldwide¹⁰, among these species, recent evaluations have assessed the conservation status of over 10,000 reptiles, revealing that nearly 20% are currently considered at risk of extinction.¹¹ Bacterial, fungal and parasitic diseases in reptiles are occasionally caused by primary pathogens but often are the result of an immunocompromising condition, such as inappropriate temperatures, humidity, or enclosure hygiene.¹²

Although some larger parasites, such as helminths,¹³ are considered pathogens, the term more commonly refers to microorganisms, including bacteria, archaea, fungi, protozoa sensu lato and viruses.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ An infection occurs when pathogens enter a host, replicate, and disrupt normal cellular or physiological processes. The effects can range from symptom-free colonization to overt disease and often involve complex interactions among microbial virulence factors, the host's immune defenses, and resident microflora.¹⁷⁻¹⁸ Some microorganisms can induce infections by invading the tissues and usually inducing diseases in healthy hosts due to their intrinsic virulence.¹⁹

Reptiles, as unique ectothermic amniotes, have immune systems that are strongly influenced by environmental conditions such as temperature and seasonal changes, unlike endothermic birds and mammals. For instance, reptiles exhibit seasonal fluctuations in lymphoid organs like the thymus and spleen, their immune cell activity and complement system efficiency depend on ambient temperature, and they can increase their body temperature through behavior in response to infection, a phenomenon similar to fever in endotherms (behavioral fever).²⁰ Over millions of years pathogenic organisms also coevolved with reptiles.²¹ Some pathogens are considered native to a specific area, while others may be translocated through various pathways, including the trafficking of wildlife.²²⁻²³

Infectious diseases have contributed significantly to declines in both captive and wild populations of reptiles and amphibians. Factors that increase the vulnerability of wild populations to such diseases include environmental stressors, such as habitat loss or degradation, exposure to pollutants, and relocation to novel environments. Animals collected from the wild are frequently exposed to unfamiliar pathogens, and additional stressors including handling, transportation, and inadequate husbandry can impair

immune function, further heightening susceptibility to infection. Moreover, the intermixing of species from distinct geographic regions during collection introduces reptiles and amphibians to pathogens to which they have no prior immunity. Evidence also suggests that certain pathogens can adapt to infect species beyond their original hosts, facilitating the emergence of novel host-pathogen interactions.²⁴

Free-living populations of reptiles and amphibians are vulnerable to a broad spectrum of infectious agents. These pathogens frequently affect captive populations when animals are exposed to individuals collected from the wild. Introduction of infectious agents into wild populations can occur through the release or escape of captive or rehabilitated animals. Because wild animals often lack prior exposure and immunity to these pathogens, they can develop disease rapidly, frequently leading to elevated morbidity and mortality.²⁵

In reptiles, a variety of infectious agents including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and parasites have been linked to illness and death in both wild and captive populations. Nevertheless, a recent review of cases at a wildlife centre revealed that infectious diseases were diagnosed in only 2% of reptiles, with most admissions resulting from trauma rather than infection.²⁶

One of the best described infectious diseases of wild populations of reptiles is mycoplasmosis in free-ranging desert tortoises (*Gopherus agassizii*) and gopher tortoises (*Gopherus polyphemus*).²⁷⁻²⁹ Viral agents have been detected in both captive and wild populations of reptiles, and in some cases have been associated with high morbidity and mortality.³⁰ Bacterial infections are often caused by organisms that are considered normal flora and part of the normal environment of the animal. The majority of the agents isolated from sick reptiles are Gram negative organisms, including *Pseudomonas* spp., *Aeromonas* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Proteus* spp., and *Klebsiella* spp. The major organ systems infected by these pathogens are the respiratory tract, gastrointestinal tract, reproductive tract, and the integumentary system.³¹ Fungi are frequently found in both wild-caught and ill captive reptiles, but they are rarely the main cause of disease. Often, they act as secondary invaders following an initial bacterial infection. Turtles and tortoises, particularly aquatic species, seem to be more prone to fungal infections compared to other types of reptiles.³²

1. Viral Diseases

Herpesvirus

Herpes virus infections have been reported in both wild and captive populations of reptiles, and are most common in chelonians.³⁰ Infected freshwater turtles include Pacific Pond turtles (*Chrysemys marmorata*), painted turtles (*Chrysemys picta*), and map turtles (*Graptemys* spp.). In tortoises, herpesvirus infection has been reported in Argentine tortoises (*Geochelone chilensis*), desert tortoises (*Gopherus agassizii*), and Mediterranean tortoises (*Testudo graeca* and *Testudo hermanni*).³²⁻³⁴ Rhinitis, pharyngitis, stomatitis, and signs of upper respiratory tract disease (URTD) are often seen in infected tortoises. Caseous, necrotizing lesions are commonly present within the oral cavity and trachea of infected tortoises.³⁵

Fibro papillomatosis

Herpesviruses have been found in marine turtles, particularly in juvenile green sea turtles (*Chelonia mydas*), where they are associated with circular, raised skin lesions (Gray-patch disease) and symptoms of upper respiratory tract disease affecting the lungs, eyes, and trachea.³⁰ Fibropapillomatosis is the most prevalent viral disease in wild marine turtles and was first recognized in the 1930s. Affected turtles typically develop visible skin growths, known as fibropapillomas, on their front flippers, neck, and around the eyes. In some cases, internal tumors can also form in organs like the lungs, stomach, liver, and kidneys.²⁴

Fig. 1. Fibro papillomatosis, green sea turtle

Source: www.msdsvetmanual.com

Paramyxovirus

Ophidian paramyxovirus (OPMV) has been identified as an important pathogen of viperid snakes in captive collections.³⁰ This disease has been reported in the United States, Central and South America, and Europe. It affects a range of snakes, including viperids, colubrids, boids, and elapids. The causative agents are viruses from the Paramyxoviridae family. Many infected snakes may not

show obvious signs, but when symptoms occur, they often include reduced appetite and respiratory issues such as labored breathing, open-mouth breathing, abnormal respiratory sounds, and mucus around the tracheal opening.²⁴

Inclusion Body Disease

Inclusion Body Disease was initially identified in captive boid snakes. It is characterized by the accumulation of eosinophilic (pink-staining) inclusion bodies within the cytoplasm of the epithelial cells in affected snakes.³⁶ This disease has been reported in the United States, Australia, Africa, and Europe, and it can cause high rates of illness and death in captive snake populations. It is unclear whether wild boid snakes also carry the disease. The causative agent is believed to be a retrovirus. Infected snakes may exhibit symptoms such as frequent vomiting, particularly in boas, and neurological problems, which are more commonly seen in pythons.²⁴

West Nile Virus

The first recorded case of West Nile Virus (WNV) in reptiles was in farmed American alligators (*Alligator mississippiensis*). The exact role of reptiles in transmitting the virus to humans remains unclear. During a 2002 WNV outbreak at alligator farms in Florida, infected alligators exhibited neurological symptoms. Laboratory tests, including immunohistochemistry and virus isolation, confirmed the infection. Researchers suggested that alligators could serve as amplifying hosts, promoting the replication and spread of WNV.³⁷

2. Bacterial Diseases

Mycoplasmosis

In the 1980s, researchers observed declines in desert tortoise populations across parts of California. Many affected tortoises exhibited symptoms of upper respiratory tract disease (URTD), including swollen eyes (conjunctivitis) and nasal discharge (rhinitis). Later in the decade, scientists identified a newly recognized bacterium, *Mycoplasma agassizii*, as the cause of the disease.²⁶⁻²⁸ Gopher tortoises in Florida were also diagnosed with the same organism shortly thereafter.²⁹ Since that time, numerous captive tortoise species have been found to carry this infection, and it is believed that all tortoise species are potentially at risk. Cases have also been documented in *Testudo graeca* (Greek tortoise) in Europe. In wild populations, the infection is more common in adults, whereas in captivity, young tortoises are also susceptible.²⁴

Salmonellosis

Salmonellosis is the most frequently transmitted disease from reptiles to humans. Caused by Gram-negative *Salmonella* bacteria, there are over 2,400 different types capable of causing illness. Both wild and captive reptiles including lizards, snakes, and turtles have been associated with human salmonella infections. Stressful conditions for reptiles, such as transportation, overcrowding, or poor husbandry, increase the likelihood of bacterial shedding.²⁴ Various Gram-negative bacteria have been associated with illnesses in wild reptiles, including species of *Aeromonas*, *Pasteurella*, *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, *Citrobacter*, *Serratia*, *Proteus*, and *Pseudomonas*. These infections can target multiple body systems, such as the skin, digestive tract, and lungs.³¹ A study of wild desert tortoises identified numerous oxygen-dependent (aerobic) bacteria in samples from their nasal passages and cloaca. Some of these bacteria, including *Pasteurella testudinis*, *Pseudomonas* species, and *Salmonella* species, have the potential to cause disease.³⁸

Fig. 2. Ulcerative dermatitis (scale rot, necrotic dermatitis), ball python

Fig. 3. Septicemic cutaneous ulcerative disease, slider turtle

Source: www.msdtvetmanual.com

3. Fungal Infections

Fungal infections have been found in many reptile species, but wild turtle populations seem to be the most frequently affected.³² Although many fungi have been detected in reptiles, only a few are recognized as primary disease-causing agents. Skin problems, including shell issues, are frequently the result of combined bacterial and fungal infections, particularly in aquatic turtles. *Fusarium* species have been reported in both terrestrial and aquatic turtles, as well as in snakes, often associated with skin injuries. Turtles also appear more prone to fungal infections in their lungs compared to other reptiles. Additionally, cases of fungal infections affecting the skin and mouth have been documented in wild pygmy rattlesnakes (*Sistrurus miliarius barbouri*) in Florida.³⁹ Infected snakes were found with necrotizing dermatitis, stomatitis, and ophthalmitis.

Fig. 4. Gray rat snake with suspect ophiomyiasis
Pic source- (Davy *et al.*, 2021)⁴¹;

4. Parasitic Infections

Pentastomids have been described in wild and captive reptiles, especially in snakes.²⁴ Cryptosporidiosis occurs worldwide and affects many reptiles, including snakes and lizards, in both wild and captive populations. The disease is transmitted via the fecal-oral route, meaning reptiles become infected by ingesting fecal-contaminated material. Some infected reptiles show no signs but can still intermittently spread the infection, while others develop symptoms such as vomiting, weight loss, and thickening of the stomach lining. In one instance, young wild-caught rough green snakes (*Ophedryx aestivus*) kept in quarantine developed severe cryptosporidiosis, resulting in serious gastrointestinal infections and high mortality.⁴⁰

Fig. 5. Myiasis, Greek tortoise

Fig. 6. Orange lizard mites (*Hirstiella*), iguana
Source: www.msdevetmanual.com

CONCLUSION

Various infectious disorders brought on by bacteria, fungus, viruses, and protozoa can affect reptiles. Turtles, snakes, and other reptiles are susceptible to viral diseases such as herpesviruses, fibropapillomatosis, and paramyxovirus, which frequently result in skin lesions, respiratory, or neurological symptoms. Fungal pathogens frequently affect the integumentary system, respiratory tract, and carapace, particularly in chelonians, whereas bacterial infections caused by *Salmonella* spp. and *Mycoplasma agassizii* are widely reported in both free-ranging and captive reptile populations. Additionally, protozoan parasites such as *Entamoeba* spp. and *Cryptosporidium* spp. represent significant health threats and may occasionally result in severe morbidity. By spreading infections, infected reptiles can harm the ecosystems, resulting in decreased biodiversity and population losses. There is urgent need to control these diseases, so that decline of biodiversity can be treated. This review provides a basic information about the diseases which affects the reptiles population and helps to gain insight on this issue.

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